

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B438
 Date: 26 Apr 2009
 Take Off: 09:30:57Z
 Landing: 14:06:34Z
 Flight Time 4h 35m 37s

Campaign: MEVEX Dust Flight 3
Operating Area: Ocean, E of Muscat

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Jon Taylor	Met Office	
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM	
6	Core Chem / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
8	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
9	SWS / SHIMS	Martin Glew	Met Office	
10	Wet Neph / CVI / IIR	Andy Wilson	Met Office	
11	MARSS	James Bowles	Met Office	
12	Mission Scientist 2	Dave Kindred	Met Office	
13	Filters	Anne Klaver	University of Paris	
14	Mini-LIDAR	Joss Kent	Met Office	
15	Obs 1	John Marsham	NCAS Leeds	
16				
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
Brief	No brief on FAAM website
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
CVI	No log passed to FAAM yet
SWS	No log passed to FAAM yet
IIR	No IIR log is provided for the Flight Folder

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	03 Nov 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20090426_r0_b438_085411_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090426_r0_b438_095411_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090426_r0_b438_105411_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090426_r0_b438_115411_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090426_r0_b438_125411_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090426_r0_b438_135411_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090426_r0_b438_115354_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090426_r0_b438_125354_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090426_r0_b438_135354_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090426_r0_b438_085354_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090426_r0_b438_095354_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090426_r0_b438_105354_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20090426_r0_b438_085400_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090426_r0_b438_095400_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090426_r0_b438_105400_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090426_r0_b438_115400_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090426_r0_b438_125400_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090426_r0_b438_135400_1hz.avi

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B438
 Date: 26th April 2009
 Project: MEVEX
 Location: Oman

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
084353		GIN	0.10 kft	001	started
091338		!	0.11 kft	267	power c/o
091714		taxy	0.10 kft	355	
091732		sample pipes	0.10 kft	356	open
092324	092626	pirouette 1	0.12 kft	269	270M
093057		T/O	3.3 kft	081	muscat
093635		JW	8.9 kft	095	zero
093659		Nev	9.4 kft	094	zero
094619	095618	transit	21.0 - 21.1 kft	093	
094638		heimann	21.0 kft	093	cal 11
095618	095919	Orbit 1	21.1 - 21.0 kft	117	fl210
095640		!	21.0 kft	158	110M 30deg rhd
100017	101528	Run 1	21.0 kft	177	
100602		bbr	21.0 kft	181	retract
101528	101706	Profile 1	21.0 - 19.6 kft	181	
101706	102713	Run 2	19.6 - 19.5 kft	181	
102539		heimann	19.5 kft	179	cal 11
103102	103639	Profile 2	19.5 - 14.1 kft	004	
103640	105202	Run 3	14.1 - 13.8 kft	003	
103906		! nev	14.1 kft	003	liquid water meters e rratic
104005		! nev	14.1 kft	003	zero - no improvement
104951		heimann	14.0 kft	003	cal 11
105202	105557	Profile 3	13.8 - 10.1 kft	002	
105815	105950	Orbit 2	10.1 kft	040	45 deg rhd 040M
110112	110232	Orbit 3	10.0 - 10.1 kft	279	50 deg lhd 280M
110653	112105	Run 4	10.1 kft	181	
112105	112834	Profile 4	10.1 - 3.1 kft	178	
113105		!	3.7 kft	034	pop up to 4000ft to s tay in layer
113134	114639	Run 5	4.1 kft	013	
114500		heimann	4.1 kft	002	cal 11
114639	115139	Profile 5	4.1 - 0.12 kft	001	
115248	115403	Orbit 4	0.95 - 0.87 kft	078	090M 50deg rhd
115651	121152	Run 6	0.21 - 0.15 kft	194	
115723		heimann	0.17 kft	188	cal 11
115832		manouver	0.16 kft	191	to avoid shipping
120815		!!	0.15 kft	181	pos reports stopped
121400	121401	Orbit 5	0.80 kft	262	270 M 55deg rhd
121435		!	0.91 kft	223	orbit 5 only exit log ged. start not called

121502	122034	Profile 6	0.90 - 6.1 kft	175
122348	123858	Run 7	6.0 kft	015
124152	125953	Profile 7	6.0 - 24.0 kft	160
130039	130530	Run 8.1	24.0 kft	180
130940	133950	Run 8.2	24.0 kft	003
131657		Sonde 1	24.0 kft	001
132639		!	24.0 kft	002 occasional twc status flash
132714		!	24.0 kft	002 using heaters s orts twc status
133629		heimann	24.0 kft	003 cal 11
133723		Sonde 2	24.0 kft	002
134434		!	24.0 kft	273 recovery to muscat
140911		ASP	0.14 kft	132 closed
140634		land	0.14 kft	265 muscat

B438 07:04:01-14:12:42

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

B438 – 26th April 2009, MEVEX Dust Study
Mission Scientist: Dr Jonathan P Taylor.

Summary

The aim of this flight was to study dust off the East coast of Oman where the Met Office CAMM forecast dust with optical depths between 0.8 and 1.6 . The US NRL model predicted no loading. The CAMM model predicted two layers one with a peak around 14 to 18000ft and a lower layer peaking at 3000ft. The model also predicted a gradient with max concentrations to the North.

The flight was very successful with high aerosol loadings found much as predicted by the CAMM although optical depth has not been computed yet.

Detail

A pirouette was performed prior to departure. On climb out the PCASP showed concentrations around 350/cc near the surface reducing to 200/cc aloft. The nephelometer indicated a lower aerosol layer that extended from the surface (blue scat = 100m-1) to 10000ft (20m-1) above 10000ft the aerosol increased again reaching a maximum at 14000ft (60m-1) before dropping to zero at 18500ft. There was a third thin layer between 18000ft and 21000ft which was easily discernable by eye on the climb out as it was distinctly separated from the main aerosol below. The aerosol between the surface and 18000ft was associated with south easterly winds the layer at 21000ft was associated with a north westerly wind. A trajectory analysis will be interesting to see the origin of these aerosol layers. The scattering was neutral Red=green=blue.

Having reached FL210 and entered the operating area an orbit was flown and SWS pointed in the nadir. A run was then flown at FL210 heading South which was skimming in the tops of the elevated aerosol layer. In this layer the PCASP was seeing around 200/cc with some larger particles being observed on the FFSSP and CDP. A subsequent run was flown at FL195 to be more in the middle of the elevated layer. We then profiled to FL140 to be in the peak of the middle layer of aerosol and flew a run at FL140 heading North. The lidar clearly showed the structure below with a minimum at 1500m below and a further peak at 2500m below the aircraft altitude. Following the run at FL140 we then profiled down to FL100 to be in the mid atmosphere minimum seen in the climb out and in the lidar data. At FL100 two orbits were flown allowing SWS to look up and down through the aerosol layers. A run at FL100 was flown from North to South – although scattering was a minimum the PCASP showed concentrations around 200/cc. A further profile was then flown from FL100 down to 4000ft to get in the middle of the most intense aerosol layer. The run at 4000ft heading North showed neph scattering of 110m-1 and PCASP concentrations of 530/cc.

A profile to 100ft was then flown followed by orbits at 800ft allowing SWS to look up through all the aerosol at the northern end of the pattern. A run was then flown heading South at 100ft followed by further orbit at the southern end of the run looking up through the lighter aerosol loadings. A run was then flown heading back North at 6000ft. During this run the PCASP concentrations were around 500/cc and scattering around 90m-1. As we headed north the aircraft came out of the aerosol which was clearly seen on the lidar which showed a gradual decrease in altitude of the aerosol

layer beneath us. A profile was then flown from 6000ft to FL240 through the complex aerosol layer structure heading South and then a short run at FL240 was carried out at FL240 to the southern most point of the pattern we had been working. A final run was then flown from FL240 heading North to the most northern point of the pattern allowing the lidar to map the aerosol below from top to bottom. Looking at the lidar in flight it was evident that the multi layered aerosol had persisted for the entire flight and that the aerosol was at a maximum at the northern end of the run. A sonde was launched at the southern and northern ends of this run to characterise the structure at the two extremes of the pattern.

Other interesting phenomena included a very strong surface duct.

In summary this was a very interesting flight with lots of structure in the aerosol which looked surprisingly similar to the prediction from the CAMM. A good case study to look at.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Jon Taylor

MEVEX

192-168101161

Flight No **B.438**
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Date 26/4/09

Page 1 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
092324	→ 092626		270		Yosemite 1 pre-flight.
093328	710				climbout aerosol canes do not look too very high. PCASP = 200/cc 350 at 5000m Temp shows stratosphere but both 12C working. FC160 above main aerosol layer Neph shows 1 layer from 5000m to 10,000ft and the another at 15000ft to 18000ft. Syrone layer associated with seen breeze?
094600					FC210 out of top of previous PCASP ≈ 400/cc 030° Census to left → same at 12000ft Dust layer more dry adiabatic than before.
095618	01	FL210	117		st 01/011 above aerosol
095830 100017	R1	FL210	198	23°18' 60°30'E	Prob a 50/60 lcc on PCASP showing tops of aerosol layer
101706	PIR2	FL195	181	28°56' 60°30'E	End dur 1 flight FL195 In elevated layer neph ≈ 10m ⁻⁴ PCASP ≈ 200 some large and FSSP and CDP seeing some.

MEVEX

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Jon TACOR

Flight No **B 438**
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Date 26/4/09

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
102627					In elevated aerosol layer although level suggests upper layer may have merged with middle layer
102713	R2	FC195			Run 2 End
103102	P2	FC195			Stg P2 ↓ FC140
103640	P/R3	FC140	003	21°42'N 60°30'E	End of P2 at FC140 Incl of neph ≈ 50 km ⁻¹
105202	R3				End R3 + start of P3
105202	P3 ↓				
105557	P3	FC100			End of P3 at FC100 in local minimum of aerosol
105815					Stg 02 Bank 045°
110112					03 Bank 050°
110653	R4	1000ft	173	23°00'N 60°30'E	Quit 011 1011 hPa
110720					Neph dropped same rate vlatg run to ≈ 32 km. 50 km ⁻¹ PASP ≈ 350 at stg run
111450				22°30'N 60°30'E	down to 210 now
112105	R4/P4 ↓	1000ft ↓	175	22°00'N 60°26'E	End Run 4 St P4 ↓ to 3000ft
112357	P4	700ft			Increasing aerosol in neph ≈ 90 km ⁻¹ Peak of 700/ce on PASP now 500/ce
112800		3500ft			Neph now 110 /ce
112834	P4	3000ft	175		End of P4
113134	R5	4000ft	013	21°02'N 60°24'E	Stg R5 ↑ in lower aerosol layer neph ≈ 110 km ⁻¹ PASP ≈ 530/ce

Aircraft Scientist's Log

MEVEX

SON TOWER

Flight No **B 438**

Date 26/6/09

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
113700	R5	4000ft			Depth remains high at ~ 110 m ² R>G>B but only small depth ~ 6m ²
					Depth cyclone impacted showing spurious readings when on depth scatter $\uparrow$ Water shows deepening as we head north and shallower space layer to north
114839	R5	4000ft	002		Endy Run 5 + sketch P5
	P5	950ft	006		top of surge duct. under at.
		200ft			Stg 0
		800ft			50° dog bank below all wind at N then endy run
115651	R6	100ft	196		Stg Run 6. Wind 207/11m/s ² Depth ~ 95 m ² .
121152	R6	100ft	178	22° 6' N 60° 26' E	End Run 6
121400					sketch orbit 55 dog bank
121502	P6		175		P6 up to 600ft $\uparrow$
122036	P6				Endy P6 turn to North
122348	R7	600ft	009	21° 48' N 60° 3' E	Stg R7 North at 600ft in ascent loop depth ~ 90m ² P6ASP ~ 490/4
					As we go North at 600ft come out of ascent loop which drifts off blow

123858 R7 600ft

End R7 600ft

Aircraft Scientist's Log

MEVEX

Sen Turner

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Date 26/4/09

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
124152	600 P7	6000ft	171	22°36'N 60°26'E	P7 Ldg South Top of aerosol layer at 18000ft minima was at 10000ft.
125953	P7	FL240	180		End of P7 ldy Sr
130039	R8-1	FL240	180	21°12'N 60°26'E	Run 8-1 Hdy South
130530	R8-1	FL240	180	20°48'N 60°30'E	End Run 8-1
130940	R8-2	FL240	005	21°0'N 60°26'E	St Run 8-2 Hdy North above all aerosol.
131717		FL240	001	21°36'N 60°26'E	Launch of Side 1 at Southern end of run BRAVO.
					Clear way to the north in G
1337		FL240	003	23°12'N 60°30'E	Launch of Side 2 at Northern end of run (ALPHA)
133949		FL240	000		End of Run 8-2 TRANSIT home

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B438** Date **26-4-09** Name **DK** Page **1** of **.....**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
092322		Start P1	27°		Start Pirouette, hdg 270°
092624		End P1			End " "
0931		T/O MUSCAT (to 2)			SKY CLEAR..
	Good PCASP	Surface / low level dust			(temp/hum)
		Grd 1700		↑ 3500 then ↓ 200	
		Both cameras working with good land views in frame.			
0937		Thin Ci above	(~25% cover)		
0947	TRANSIT	21000ft	093°		Ci to N.
					Nept ↓ almost nil, Aerosol into comb (low) & top 'lid' to main BL ~ 20-21000ft.
095618	PERIT 1	21,000		23° 24' N 60° 30' E	START ↓ orbit 30°.
095915					END orbit.
100017	START R1	21,000	198°	23° 18' N 60° 30' E	Wind 293 / 4m/sec
1002				→	PCASP 5060 ;
101528	END R1, START R2	21,000	187°	23° 00' N 60° 30' E	
101706	END R1, START R2	19,000	19°		Start 2 min run (extra run)
1027	END R2				Turning ↓ & next run will be S → N (after P2 to R1 to)
103102	START P2		001°	21° 12' N 60° 30' E	Descent to 14,000'.
103640	END P2, START R3		003°		At 14,000' (IN AEROSOL)
1053		Descending ↓ to next level (10,000').			
105557	END R3	10,000'	006°		Prepare for orbits.
105805	START ORBIT 2		45°	040°	✓ v. good orbit. FROM SWS.
110112	START ORBIT 3		50°	280°	✓ good orbit, Continue auto S → N track & perform 15 min SCL run.
1106	START R4	10000'	173°	23° 00' N 60° 30' E	PWH=1011 Wind 120/20m/sec.
112125	END R4/P4	10000'	178°	22° 00' N 60° 24' E	107/12m/sec.
112834	END P4	3000'			Turning ↓
113134	START R5	4000'			SCL run in (lower) aerosol layer (thicker here than at 3000')

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B438** Date **26-4-09** Name **JLK** Page **2** of **2**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
114639	END PS PS	4000'	001°		Descending to 100'.
	Temp. inv.				humidity ↘ at 900'.
115139	END PS	50'	004°	60°30'E 23°00'N	EXCELLENT SURFACE RADAR SWCT (LOW REVERB) (almost 40°C change in DewPt on GIE).
11	START ORBIT	50'	088°	To 800T	GOOD ORBIT SWCT.
1156	START RL	100'	151°	23°54'N 60°24'E	205°/5m/sec.
120000	R6	100'	194°	22°48'N 60°24'E	203°/5m/sec. Temp 29.4°C 19.6°C.
121432	R6	100'	177°		
1213	START ORBIT	55'			Good orbit ✓
121502	START P6	CLIMB TO 6000'			
122034	END P6	6000'			
122348	START R7	6000'			SAL TEN.
123858	END R7	6000'			TURN AROUND & CLIMB ↑ FL240.
1300	END P7	FL240			
130530	END RW 8	FL240			(at B - extended) : Turn ↗ (run B → A at FL240 dropping 1 sande either end of leg.
130940		START RW 8.2			AT B (→ A).
131658					Sande # 1 DROPPED (Not A, but 7 mins into run)
133725					Sande # 2 " "
1345					ON RETURN LEG TO MUSCAT.
1406		LAND			MUSCAT.
0931	T/O				
4135m					

Paul Vetter ^{um} run?

Clearing down 12km² effect.

Veg Low RH

Controlled Variables

Aircraft Scientist's Log

at top of extended leg (unclear tp).

Sea breeze

Flight No **B438** Date 26/6/09 Name JOHN MARSHAM Page 1 of 3

Orbit/
height log

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
09:00	-	Ground		Muxat	Vis slightly deteriorating? Mod vis in air
					Some Ci. 1/8 at most. Some dust (geos) visible.
					Thick Neph ↑ at 08:00 Real? 80% to 100.
09:20					Neph: B > G > R, 70 > 50 > 40 ↑
09:23:22	-	G		Muxat	Pirattto 1 start 270°
09:26:26	-	"		"	End Pirattto 1 270°
09:30:56		∅ - 920ft		"	Take-off & along coast → sea.
09:34					Coast sea → land.
09:46	End of Profile ∅				Dusty sea haze. ~ 80% 100 ft to 500 ft
09:44					Ci to L End Pirattto 2
09:56		21kft.		23°N 60°E	Orbit 30° Start
10:00:17	#1	21kft.	180°	23°15'N 60°30'E	Start Run 1
10:05:28	End 1	21kft → 19kft	180°		End run Pirattto 1. Start Profile 1 ↓
10:17:04		19.5kft	182°		Start Run 2. neph ~ 155'
					neph ~ uniform. but RH decrease in air.
					Cloud tech correlated with neph? Yes.
10:27:13					End Run 2.
10:31:36					(Td cloud eaten error).
10:31:36	36	19.5kft ↓	1°		Start Profile 2 ↓
10:36:36		16kft -	3°		End Profile 2 16kft Start Run 3 (5913kft)
10:47					Run 3 under! neph visible
					Neph inside in Run 3: 30 to 70 (m) -
10:51:46		4 ↓ 10kft	2°		End Run 3. Start Profile 3
10:52:02 (FM)					
10:55:15		10kft			End Profile 3.
10:58:15					Start Orbit

10:58:10

Orbit (Only selected plots)

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B438** Date 26/4/09 Name John Mahan Page 2 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:01:12					Orbit 50° (no 3)
to 11:					
11:05:59		10kft	175°		Run 4 Start (896 hPa) Again neph very wide: min 230'W Neph inc correlated wth humidity → Anticir. neph O ₃ not temp? Low & high det
11:21:08		10kft	177°		End Run 4 Start public ↓ Run 4 neph inc to N
11:28:37		↳ to 3kft.			End Public 4. Turn and (300' cirrus det just?)
11:30:43		↑ to 4kft.	N		Turn
11:31:33		4kft	10°		Run 5 Start (872 hPa) 900 to 800 hPa Much more dry adiabatic. Where was this? (11:21 to 11:28 UTC) → 21.8W 1/2 way along leg. Cluster too Much more central neph.
11:46:36		4kft 100'	N		End Run 5. Start Public 5 ↓ to 100' Neph drop at 912 hPa 100' Td decay. det decr 118L
11:51:41		100'	N		End of Public 5 [1 leg shallow 118L clear?]
11:52:56					Orbit 80°
11:56:58		100'	S		Run 6 Start Neph ~ 100' T _d = 21, T = 30°C, B = 93 G = 94, R = 96
12:01:56		100'			End run 6. Climb to 300 800'. Orbit 55°
12:11:06		800' to 600'	S		Public 6 ↑
12:20:26		600'	Slow N.		End of Public 6. Turn and

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B438** Date **26/6/09** Name **JOHN MACKIN** Page **3** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:23:46	R7	6000'	N		Stat Run 7. Neph dec 2 Td dec along run. 100 to 40 (line alt end)
12:38:55					Neg $\alpha \frac{1}{9}$, Neg $\alpha 9$, End Run 7
12:41:10	P	6400' 2400'	S		6000' up to 2400' neph $\alpha 60$ ₄₀ N no compute
13:01:30					End Run
13:09:40		2400'			Stat Run 8.2 (at B) Soud after B Good lidar data, Soud near A
13:20					End Run 8.2 Neph decreased S to $\emptyset$ $\emptyset$ increased $332.7 \rightarrow 335.5$ q incd 0.2 to 0.6 At constant height $\rightarrow$ Leaving plume.
13:49		2400'			
14:00:13					Com wat? Pyradialate 900-8000Pa BL top? 7975 Marine rept 50. see log?
14:06:42		G			Land. Neph ~ 50 Clearer on lastest than take-off.
					Two well mixed aerosol layers separated by clear stable layer. Some fine structure. Very shallow MSL. Maxal diffed from Ocean. Sea haze decreased. N $\rightarrow$ gradient in dust over sea (Consistent variable diameter).

JMM Re-take off

New plot, same times

Flight B438 09:39:50

Heading 94 deg Speed 287 knots Height 13.8kft Press 599mb

Lat 23°30.0'N Long 58°54.0'E Wind 2 ms-1/ 76 deg

Temp 4.24C Dewpoint -15.46C

From 07:00:24 to 09:29:00

*Sea Bgc
Ldub. ?
or instruments!*

Current values			
— TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	34788	secs	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
— NONDEICED INDICATED AIR TEMP	13.98	deg C	<input type="radio"/>

Jim

Run 4

Flight B438 11:23:02

Heading 173 deg Speed 231 knots Height 8.0kft Press 750mb

Lat 22°0.0'N Long 60°30.0'E Wind 12 ms-1/ 106 deg

Temp 15.51C Dewpoint -11.98C

From 11:05:59 to 11:21:05

Current values			
+++++ SPECIFIC HUMIDITY	2.03	g kg-1	⊙ All
NEPH BLUE SP	28.71	m-1	○

NEPH 29.

Sum Run 4

Flight B438 11:21:58

Heading 176 deg Speed 242 knots Height 9.1kft Press 720mb

Lat 22°0.0'N Long 60°24.0'E Wind 12 ms-1/ 107 deg

Temp 13.85C Dewpoint -12.82C

From 11:05:59 to now

Current values			
GPS LATITUDE	22.08	deg (+ve N)	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
NEPH BLUE SP	22.65	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
NEPH GREEN SP	26.03	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
NEPH RED SP	29.27	m-1	<input type="radio"/>

*neph increasing northwards.
Variations α g .*

JMM

Flight B438 12:41:04

Heading 121 deg Speed 230 knots Height 6.0kft Press 810mb

Lat 22°42.0'N Long 60°24.0'E Wind 7 ms-1/ 116 deg

Temp 20.45C Dewpoint -11.22C

From 12:23:47 to 12:38:55

Run 7

Current values
POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE 311.79 K ● All
NEPH BLUE SP 50.96 m-1 ○

$neph \propto \frac{1}{\theta}$

B438-#mevexViRClog

```
*** Opened channel log for #mevex at 26/04/2009 09:57:25
[2009/04/26 09:57] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/26 09:57] <FAAM> first orbit in progress
[2009/04/26 09:58] [FAAMOpsDetach] Good. Were there problems with the filters pre take-off?
[2009/04/26 10:01] <FAAM> yes - Ill get Dave to gives the current situation
[2009/04/26 10:03] [FAAMOpsDetach] okay
[2009/04/26 10:05] <FAAM> worried about some leakage on one , Dave is going forward to check flows
now
[2009/04/26 10:10] <FAAM> investigations continue
[2009/04/26 10:25] *** Server connection lost
[2009/04/26 10:25] *** Server connection lost
[2009/04/26 10:30] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/26 10:32] [FAAMOpsDetach] seem to be having some server problems at this end...
[2009/04/26 10:40] <FAAM> this end seems stable enough
[2009/04/26 10:44] <FAAM> nevezorov liquid water is extremely erratic raw collector counts are
fluctuating wildly
[2009/04/26 10:45] <FAAM> almost regular oscillations in all liquid water parameters, total water
appears stable
[2009/04/26 10:59] [FAAMOpsDetach] ..and this is in clear air?
[2009/04/26 11:03] <FAAM> in first dust layer
[2009/04/26 11:08] <FAAM> both units now stable
[2009/04/26 11:12] <FAAM> plots emailed to masmi
[2009/04/26 11:13] [FAAMOpsDetach] okay
[2009/04/26 11:23] <FAAM> outlook express failed during send, which was very slow
[2009/04/26 11:23] <FAAM> plots in flight folder
[2009/04/26 11:29] [FAAMOpsDetach] For Martin G - one DHL package is held up in Dubai, the other
has cleared customs in Muscat. I've been assured they will both be delivered
to me by 1200 tomorrow
[2009/04/26 11:33] <FAAM> thumbs up & cheery smile (?) from Martin
[2009/04/26 11:38] [FAAMOpsDetach] good!
[2009/04/26 11:42] [FAAMOpsDetach] Re Joss's poorly arm - I enquired of the hospital, they have
24hrs GP cover. Plan A - Joss comes back to hotel post flight, quick splash
then I take him to hosp. Can you check if this okay with Joss?
[2009/04/26 11:48] <FAAM> sounds good to Joss
[2009/04/26 11:49] [FAAMOpsDetach] Top
[2009/04/26 11:50] [FAAMOpsDetach] Are you going to try the posn rep stealth plan?
[2009/04/26 11:59] <FAAM> yes stealth plan as soon as the plan settles down!
[2009/04/26 12:00] [FAAMOpsDetach] okay, I can picture the scene!
[2009/04/26 12:06] <FAAM> about to stop satcom position reports
[2009/04/26 12:07] <FAAM> satcom position reports stopped
[2009/04/26 12:09] [FAAMOpsDetach] Can Martyn give us an update on the status of the new PCASP ie
any new information/hints
[2009/04/26 12:10] [FAAMOpsDetach] No posn reports on web since 1150Z
[2009/04/26 12:11] <FAAM> test satcom email to masmi with pos reports suppressed
[2009/04/26 12:15] [FAAMOpsDetach] No emails received so far...
[2009/04/26 12:16] <FAAM> email AND position reports are queued!
[2009/04/26 12:17] [FAAMOpsDetach] is one of the msgs in "Issued" status?
[2009/04/26 12:19] <FAAM> no, neither email 12:10:46, or pos reps 12:13:07, 12:16:44 have been
issued, static as queued
[2009/04/26 12:19] [FAAMOpsDetach] It would be worth using option 10 to stop and resubmit one of
them, see if that jump starts it into action
[2009/04/26 12:25] <FAAM> stopping works resubmission doesn't seem to
[2009/04/26 12:29] <FAAM> martyn : well by adjusting sp200 several faults ----- he is blethering --
big noise problems associated with sws
[2009/04/26 12:31] <FAAM> about to log off and reconfigure
[2009/04/26 12:31] *** FAAM (~GLUXE@203.38.13.45) has left #mevex
[2009/04/26 12:35] *** FAAM_flt_manage (~GLUXE@203.38.13.45) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/26 12:35] *** FAAM_flt_manage (~GLUXE@203.38.13.45) has left #mevex
[2009/04/26 12:37] *** FAAM_flt_man (~GLUXE@203.38.13.45) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/26 12:37] <FAAM_flt_man> back again
[2009/04/26 12:38] [FAAMOpsDetach] any update on the ETA?
[2009/04/26 12:42] <FAAM_flt_man> position reports restarted
[2009/04/26 12:44] <FAAM_flt_man> initial estimet is 14:30 but liable to adjustment
[2009/04/26 12:46] [FAAMOpsDetach] thanks, engs were enquiring
[2009/04/26 12:52] <FAAM_flt_man> could you ask peter for a weather update please
[2009/04/26 12:52] [FAAMOpsDetach] on its way
[2009/04/26 12:54] <FAAM_flt_man> flt man leaving group to connect ms3
[2009/04/26 12:54] *** FAAM_flt_man (~GLUXE@203.38.13.45) has left #mevex
[2009/04/26 12:56] [FAAMOpsDetach] hello mission
[2009/04/26 13:08] [FAAMOpsDetach] posn report rcvd at 1246 but none since
[2009/04/26 13:23] *** FAAM_MS3 (~GLUXE@203.38.13.16) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/26 13:23] <FAAM_MS3> mission sci 3 now on test
[2009/04/26 13:27] <FAAM_MS3> Hi Mo . R U receiving me ??
[2009/04/26 13:28] [FAAMOpsDetach] rx ok
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[2009/04/26 13:30] <FAAM_MS3> Great ! An interesting flight so far - good structure of aerosol layers & excellent agreement between wetneph, lidar and Tephigrams. ETA 1415 z

[2009/04/26 13:35] [FAAMOpsDetach] super!

[2009/04/26 13:37] [FAAMOpsDetach] Dave, please can you ask Joss to let us know what time he will be at the security gate (after landing)? Steve D will meet him there

[2009/04/26 13:39] <FAAM_MS3> Message from Dougie: Pse cud u bring the ethernet crossover cable from the box in MEVEX room (ethernet cables) -to the airport. Longer cable required.

[2009/04/26 13:40] <FAAM_MS3> Message from Joss:Will meet Steve after post flight brief @ approx 1500z

[2009/04/26 13:42] <FAAM_MS3> Mo: who's winning the Bahrain Grand Prix ?

[2009/04/26 13:44] <FAAM_MS3> Pse cud Mo also bring in sicky tape to seal sondes (for Doug)

[2009/04/26 13:49] *** FAAM_MS3 (~GLUXE@203.38.13.16) has quit IRC

[2009/04/26 13:56] [FAAMOpsDetach] Button won

*** Closed channel log for #mevex at 26/04/2009 13:57:04

Cloud Physics Flight Log B438

Date:26/04/09	Operator: MAP	DRS Time:06:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	AUX1 Time: +0	AUX2 Time: +0
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DAU2 Disk space?

	PCASP SPP-200		CDP		PCASP		2DC		FFSSP		SID3	
Operated?												
Pre-flight checks	Vref	7.6	Ref V (~3):	2.05	Vref (>7):	Unknown	El#1 V (>1):	-1.9	Ref V:	3.3	Comms?	No
	Sample flow	1.32			Flow (~1):	0.7	El#32 V (>1):	-1.9				
	Sheath flow	17.6			Pressure:	1010						
					Temp (NDIT)	31.7						

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
09:45:20	FL200												Heaters off
09:56:18	FL210												Start Orbits
09:59:43													End of Orbits
10:00:28	FL210												Start Run 1
10:01:00		0		60	0.2	50	0.06				4		Ch1 noise in old PCASP (some ch2 also)
10:03:00		0		60	0.2	50	0.06						Ch1 noise in old PCASP (some ch2 also)
10:05:00		0		55	0.2	50	0.06						Ch1 noise in old PCASP (some ch2 also)
10:07:00		0		60	0.2	55	0.06						Ch1 noise in old PCASP (some ch2 also)
10:09:00		0		40	0.2	Noise	0.06						Ch1 noise in old PCASP (some ch2 also)
10:11:00		0		35	0.2	65	0.06						Ch1 noise in old PCASP (some ch2 also)
10:13:00		0		40	0.2	Noise							Ch1 noise in old PCASP (some ch2 also)
10:15:31	FL210	0											End of Run 1 & Start Profile 1
10:16:33	FL200	0		80									
10:17:06	FL195												End of Profile 1 & Start Run 2
10:18:00				80	0.6	Noise					5		
10:20:00		0.1		70	0.7	Noise							
10:22:00		0.1		60	0.7	Noise							
10:24:00		0.1		Noise		70	0.07						
10:26:00		0.1		80	1	70	0.07						
10:27:14													End of Run 2
10:31:03	FL195												Start Profile 2
10:31:39	FL190	0.1		70	1	80	0.08						
10:32:32	FL180	0.1		90	1	110	0.10						

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
10:33:30	FL170	0.1		90	1	100	0.09						
10:34:31	FL160	0.1		90	1	110	0.10						
10:35:32	FL150	0.1		110	1.5	130	0.11						
10:36:40	FL140												End of P2 & Start Run 3
10:37:00		0.1		100	1.5	100	0.12				6		Old PCASP noise mostly gone
10:39:00		0.1		120	1.5	100	0.12						
10:41:00		0.1		120	1.5	100	0.12						
10:43:00		0.1		120	1.5	100	0.13				7		
10:45:00		0.1		130	1.5	80	0.14						
10:47:00		0.1		130	1.5	85	0.13						
10:49:00		0.1		130	1.5	85	0.13				8		
10:51:47													End of Run & Start Profile 3
10:52:52	FL130	0.1		150	1.5	110	0.13						
10:53:53	FL120	0.1		160	1.5	120	0.12						
10:54:55	FL110	0.1		275	2	220	0.09				9		
10:55:59	FL100	0.1		300	2	280	0.09						End of Profile 3
10:58:23													Start Orbits
11:02:40													End Orbits
11:06:04	FL100												Start Run 4
11:07:00		0.1		450	1.5	340	0.08				10		
11:09:00		0.1		400	1.5	300	0.08				11		
11:11:00		0.1		300	1.5	230	0.09						
11:13:00		0.1		300	1.5	220	0.09						
11:15:00		0.1		300	1.5	180	0.09				12		
11:17:00		0.1		200	1.5	160	0.09						
11:19:00		0.1		200	1.5	160	0.09						
11:21:20													End of Run 4 & Start Profile 4
11:21:59	FL090	0.1		450	2	300	0.09						
11:23:09	FL080	0.15		500	2	500	0.09						
11:24:06	FL070	0.3	7	500	2	500	0.09				13		
11:25:17	FL060	0.3	7	480	2	490	0.09						
11:26:30	FL050	0.3	10	500	2	560	0.09						
11:27:32	FL040	0.3	10	500	2	610	0.09				14		
11:28:37	3000'	0.3	10	500	2	650	0.09						End of Profile 4 Heaters off
11:31:38	4000'												Start Run 5
11:32:00		0.3	7	500	2	530	0.09				15		

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
11:34:00	4000'	0.3	7	500	1.5	510	0.09				15		
11:36:00		0.3	7	550	2	500	0.09				16		
11:38:00		0.3	7	550	2	500	0.09						
11:40:00		0.3	7	550	2	515	0.09				17		
11:42:00		0.3	7	600	1.5	500	0.09						
11:44:00		0.3	7	550	1.5	480	0.09				18		
11:46:00		0.3	7	550	2	500	0.09						
11:46:42													End of Run & Start Profile 5
11:47:40	3000'	0.3	7	600	2	600	0.08				19		
11:48:38	2000'	0.4	7	300	2	370	0.09						
11:49:48	1000'	0.3	7	300	2	270	0.09						
11:51:39	100'	0.3	6	500	2	600	0.09				20		End of Profile
11:52:55													Start of Orbits
11:53:50													End of Orbits
11:56:53	100'												Start Run 6
11:57:00		0.2	5	300	2	400	0.09				21		
11:59:00		0.3	5	550	2	550	0.09						
12:01:00		0.3	5	500	2	600	0.08				22		
12:03:00		0.3	5	350	2	450	0.09						
12:05:00		0.3	5	450	2	480	0.09				23		
12:07:00		0.2	7	400	2	400	0.09						
12:09:00		0.2	7	400	2	450	0.09				24		
12:11:00		0.2	7	400	2	400	0.09						
12:11:55													End of Run 6
12:13:00													Start Orbits
12:14:06													End of Orbits
12:15:05	900'	0.2	5	200	2	225	0.09				25		Start Profile 6
12:16:12	FL020	0.15	5	350	2	380	0.09						
12:17:14	FL030	0.2	7	500	2	460	0.09				26		
12:18:27	FL040	0.2	7	500	2	400	0.09						
12:19:18	FL050	0.3	7	450	2	400	0.09						
12:20:28	FL060												End of Profile
12:23:50	FL060												Start Run 7
12:24:00		0.3	7	500	2	450	0.09				27		
12:26:00		0.3	7	600	2	420	0.09				28		
12:28:00		0.3	7	500	2	400	0.09				29		

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
12:30:00		0.3	7	500	2	400	0.09				29		
12:32:00		0.3	7	500	2	380	0.09						
12:34:00		0.3	7	500	2	360	0.08						
12:36:00		0.25	7	500	2	370	0.08						
12:38:00		0.25	7	500	2	400	0.08				30		
12:38:58													End of Run
12:41:53	FL060												Start Profile 8
12:43:08	FL070	0.25	7	500	2	410	0.08						
12:44:21	FL080	0.2	7	350	2	250	0.08						
12:45:18	FL090	0.2	7	250	1.5	150	0.08						
12:46:14	FL100	0.2	7	200	1.5	110	0.08				31		
12:47:25	FL110	0.2	7	200	1.5	80	0.12						
12:48:20	FL120	0.2	7	150	1.5	85	0.12						
12:49:18	FL130	0.2	7	100	1.5	75	0.14						
12:50:23	FL140	0.2	7	100	1.5	60	0.12						
12:51:18	FL150	0.2	7	100	1.5	70	0.12						
12:52:20	FL160	0.2	7	100	1.5	40	0.12				32		Heaters on
12:53:16	FL170	0.2	7	100	1.5	45	0.12						
12:54:11	FL180	0.2	7	70	1	35	0.12						
12:55:11	FL190	0.1	7	70	1	40	0.10						
12:56:28	FL200			50	1	30	0.06						
12:57:15	FL210			30	1	30	0.06						Some noise in CH1 on Old PCASP starting
12:58:15	FL220			30	0.5	20	0.07						
12:59:07	FL230			30	0.5	35	0.07						
12:59:56	FL240			40	0.5	40	0.06						End of Profile
13:00:34	FL240												Start Run 8.1
13:01:00				60	0.5	55	0.06						
13:03:00				60	0.5	Noise							
13:05:00				60	0.5	Noise							
13:05:25													End of Run
13:09:45	FL240												Start Run 8.2
13:10:00				50	0.5	Noise							
13:12:00				50	0.5	Noise							
13:14:00				50	0.5	Noise							
13:16:00				50	0.5	Noise							
13:18:00				50	0.5	Noise							

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B438

Date:

26-04-09

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)	Bottom inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)
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Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1	B438-N16	----	----	Bottom	10:37:43	10:53:10		249	FL 140
Filters run1	B438-N17	----	----	Top	10:37:43	10:53:10		391	
Filters run 2	B438-N18	----	----	Bottom	11:33:01	11:46:38		159	4000 ft
Filters run 2	B438-N19	----	----	Top	11:33:01	11:46:38		164	
Filters run 3	B438-N20	----	----	Bottom	12:25:02	12:38:37		159	6000 ft
Filters run 3	B438-N21	----	----	Top	12:25:02	12:38:37		173	
Filters run 4	B438-N22	----	----	Bottom					Blanks(made at inconstant altitude)
Filters run 4	B438-N23	----	----	Top					
	B438-N24	----	----	Bottom					Lab blank

161

Flight:

B438

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:
 Heimann:
 Deiced Temp:
 Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:
 Buck CR2:
 General Eastern:
 Johnson Williams:
 Nevzorov:
 Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:
 Forward Facing:
 Rearward Facing:
 Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:
 GIN Applanix:
 INU Honeywell:
 Radar Altimeter:
 RVSM IAS:
 RVSM Static Pressure:
 XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:
 AMTG:
 AVAPS:
 Cabin Pressure:
 Printer:
 S9 Static Pressure:
 Satcom C:
 Satcom H (VIRC):
 Turb Centre-Static:
 Turb Left Right:
 Turb Up-Down:
 Turb Horizontal Chk:
 Turb Vertical Chk:
 Weather Radar:
DLUs:
 DLU AERACK:
 DLU BBR Lower:
 DLU BBR Upper:
 DLU Core Chem:
 DLU Core Consoles:
 DLU Port Aft:
 DLU Port Fwd:
 DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:
 BBR (clear) Lower:
 BBR (IR) Lower:
 BBR (red) Lower:
Upper:
 BBR (clear) Upper:
 BBR (IR) Upper:
 BBR (red) Upper:
 ARIES:
 DEIMOS:
 IR Camera:
 JNO2 Lower:
 JNO2 Upper:
 JO1D Lower:
 JO1D Upper:
 MARSS:
 SHIMS Lower:
 SHIMS Upper:
 SWS:
 TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:
 2DP:
 FFSSP:
 PCASP:
 PCASP SPP-200:
 2DS:
 ADA:
 CAPS:
 CCN:
 CDP (fuselage):
 CDP (Canister):
 CIP 100 (PIP):
 CIP 25 (CIP):
 CPI:
 CVI (Inlet):
 CVI PCASP-X:
 CVI Ly-A Hygro:
 FSSP (UMan):
 SID1:
 SID2:
 SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:
 CPC 3786 H2O:
 Filters 47mm:
 Filters 90mm:
 Neph - Dry:
 Neph - Wet:
 PSAP:
 AMS:
 CPC (AMS):
 SMPS (AMS):
 CPC 3010A (CVI):
 INC:
 Mini-LIDAR:
 SP2:
 UHSAS:
 VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:
 NOx TE42C:
 Ozone TE49C:
 Ozone TE49:
 SO2 TE43C:
 TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
 TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
 FAGE:
 Formaldehyde:
 NOx FAAM:
 NOxy:
 ORAC:
 PAN:
 PERCA:
 Peroxide:
 PTRMS:
 TDLAS (1C):
 WAS Bags:
 WAS Bottles:
Misc Non-Core
 CASI/ATM:
 LIDAR (big):
 LTI:
 SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B438
Date: 26rd April 2009

Instruments

cloud physics

SID3 not operated
old pcasp works ok below fl180, noisy above
new pcasp noise from SWS 28V ?

CVI – ok

IIR – good

wet neph returns zero above 3000ft

dry neph ok

Nevezorov some erratic data and failed sensor

Chemistry – good data

AVAPS – some difficulty getting gps signal in aircraft but 2 sondes good data

MARSS – good data

SWS/SHIMS -lower shims not operated

ARIES – good data

Mini Lidar – good data

filters – volumes improved after preflight work. possible vol 1 leak

FWVS – PC crashes at low level

SATCOM-H: serviceable

GIN – serviceable

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

^ Clipboard power button

Date: 26/4/09

Flight No: B438

Pre-Flighter: PDZ

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	X	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	X	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	Core Chem detector
3	✓	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	✓	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	✓	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	✓	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	✓	HORACE	Recording data	
8	✓	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9		HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	✓	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	✓	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12		GPS	Checked	
13		INU	Align	
14	✓	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	X	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	X	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	X	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	NOT FITTED
18	X	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	✓	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
20	✓	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	✓	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	✓	GE	Balance checked	
23	✓	INU	Navigate then back to Align	REVT FAULT = 1
			XREM GPS	

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	✓	CNC	WATER Butanol fitted	ALL COMPLETE - FORMS TO BE A FAULT.
25	X	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	DRY NEPH OPERATOR.
26	✓	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
27	X	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	NOT FITTED
28				
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	✓	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	✓	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	✓	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	✓	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	✓	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	✓	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	✓	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	✓	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	✓	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	✓	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	✓	All other covers	Removed	
40		Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	✓	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
42		Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
43		Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
44	✓	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
45		ICEX applied		
46	✓	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) ✓ b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
47	✓	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

NB This is an old sheet

ARIES flight log

Flight: B 438

page 1 of 3

Date: 26/Apr/09 Operator(s): S. Beeson

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: MEVEX: Dust flight

Scans: either "[IGMs][co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
~0615	—	Power UP			OK		After checking all-OK, turned
~0930	Take off.						targets off to help keep things cool.
094810	FL210	cal	CH	0	81	42	CHcal wind ~ 39 C mirror 13 C
095254	"	N3min	N	0	81	37	N3min macro CBB probably not stable yet.
095619	O1						Nadir in ^{30°} orbit, matching SWS —
10 5935 5935	FL210	Z1min	Z	0	81	31	Z1min macro CBB OK?
10 0220	"	N3min	N	0	81	31	N3min
10 0607	"	240 x1	Z	0	81	31	Zenith
10 0926	"	N3min	N	0	81	30	Nadir
10 1537	P↓	cal	CH	0	81	30	CHcal.
10 1714	FL195?	240 x1	N	0	81	31	Nadir
10 1940		240 x1	N	0	81	30	Nadir
10 2150		cal	CH	0	81	31	CHcal.
10 2311		240 x1	Z	0	81	31	Zenith
10 2459		240 x1	N	0	81	31	Nadir
10 2706		cal	CH	0	81	31	CHcal
10 3648	FL140	Z1min	Z	0	81	31	Z1min
10 3834	"	N3min	N	0	81	31	N3min
10 44 -	"	240 x1	Z	0	81	31	Zenith
10 4530	"	260 x1	N	0	81	31	Nadir
10 4744	"	cal	CH	0	81	31	CHcal
10 4911	"	480 x1	N	0	81	31	Nadir Murky dust below
10 5322	P↓	cal	CH	0	81	31	CHcal
10 5545	FL100	cal	CH	0	81	31	CHcal.
10 5815	O2	240 x1	Z	0	81	31	Zenith in orbit 45°
10 5954		cal	CH	0	81	31	CHcal
11 0114	O3	240 x1	Z	0	81	31	Zenith in orbit 50° (Z start a few seconds late)
11 0245		cal	CH	0	81	31	CHcal.
11 0425		cal	CH	0	81	31	CHcal
11 0544	FL100	240 x1	Z	0	81	31	Zenith
11 0813		240 x1	N	0	81	31	Nadir

ARIES flight log

Flight: B 438 page 2 of 3

Date: _____ Operator(s): _____ Res: _____ Gain A: _____ B: _____

Loc./Notes: _____

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
11 10 28	FL100	240x1	Z	0	81	31	Zenith
11 11 39		cal	CH	0	81	31	CH cal.
11 13 31		240x1	N	0	81	31	Nadir.
11 15 26		240x1	Z	0	81	31	Zenith
11 17 39		240x1	N	0	81	31	Nadir.
11 19 43	P↓	cal	CH	0	81	31	CH cal.
11 23 55		cal	CH	0	81	31	CH cal.
11 29 33		cal	CH	0	81	32	CH cal.
11 31 35	^{res} 4000ft	120x1	N	0	81	33	Nadir
11 32 53		360x1	Z	0	81	33	Nadir
11 35 45		N 2 3min	Z	0	81	33	Nadir ??
11 37		360x1	Z	0	81	33	Zenith ??
11 38		120x1	N	0	81	33	Nadir
11 39 29		360x1	Z	0	81	35	Zenith 11 40 35 Cps set to 40% as it's sticking to float at ambient. window: 30C Mirror: 30C
11 42 31		cal.	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
11 43 58		360x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
11 45 25		360x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
11 46 40	P↓	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
11 50 30	100ft	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal
11 52 52	0-600ft	240x1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith during orbit
11 54 27		cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal
11 56 43	100ft	240x1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith
11 59 29		120x1	N	0	81	43	Nadir (Following Heiman cal)
12 00 57		Z 1min	Z	0	81	42	Z 1min - continuing in orbit.
	0 500ft						55° orbit.
12 14 40	↑	cal	CH	0	81	43	CH cal.
12 20 19	6000ft	cal	CH	0	81	43	CH cal
12 23 49		360x1	Z	0	81	43	Zenith
12 26 01		cal	CH	0	81	43	CH cal.
12 27 22		240x1	N	0	81	42	Nadir
12 29 30		360x1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	26/04/09	Flight	B438	log pages
Operator(s)	J.Bowles	Campaign	MEVEX			
Departure	Muscat	Arrival	Muscat			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						Y	
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•	
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•	
FERA on					at time	05:53	
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	29°C	Ch	30°C	Ch18	30°C	
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on					at time	05:55	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	303	Cold	309			
Target heating						Y	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•	
Scanning on (LMD box)					at time		
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual		•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software					at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	09:09:40		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.66	Cold	314.79	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	40.24	31	38.2	40.95	40.82	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again					at time	

Double 'Dry' Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.438**.....

 Date 26/4/09.....

 Operator's name: A. Wilson.....

 Page 1 of 2.....

GMT	Run	Height	Cyclone On?	Inlet RH	Dry neph flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph flow	Wet neph RH	Remarks
			WET Neph						PREFLIGHT OK. BOTH NEPHS ZERO OK.
063000 093328									TAKE OFF: BOTH NEPHS RECORDING PROFILE OUT.
	TRANSIT	FL210							
095957	R1	FL210			15		13.8		Start R1 above aerosol.
104109	R1	"							end R1 and profile to FL195
101706	R2	FL195			15				Start R2 in light aerosol layer
102713	R2	"			15		14		end R2 and profiling to FL140
103640	R3	FL140			15		16.2		Start R3 in good dust layer. Dry neph OK but Wet neph not seeing it to get.
105202	R3	FL140			15		18		end R2 and profiling to FL100 for orbits
110259	R4	FL100			15		13.6		START R4. WET NEPH still dubious! Static Pressure Cabin 974mb. 979mb.
112105	R4	FL100			15		13.8		end R4 and profiling to 3000ft.
112740									Wet neph back!! static 883mb cabin pressure 979mb
113134	R5	4000ft			15		14.7		start R5
113348		"			15		9.9		adjust cyclone flow to 9.9, values drop? why?
113620		"			15		15.2		" " " " 15.2 values increase! why??
113715		"			15		6.3		" " " " 6.3 values drop again! why???
114000		"			15		15.1		" " " " 15.2 values increase again! why??
114505					15		7.4		" " " " 7.5 values decrease!!!!
11	R45				15		7.4		end R45. Profiling down to 100ft

ALS450 LIDAR FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT NUMBER: B438
 DATE: 26/04/09
 Campaign: MEVEX

OPERATOR: Joss
 WATER FILL: Boeing/Boeing refill
 WATER EMPTY:
 Ct: 612456
 Cw: 612456

afternoon cross over cable

Run No:	Altitude	Start Time	Stop Time	Int. Time	Head Temp	Water Temp	Notes
T1	FL200	0936	0944	100/s	38	37.8	
T2	FL210	094730	095618	1200/60	37	37.5	
R1		090000	09153	1200/60			
P1	FL210	091528	091800	100/s			
R2	FL195	091718	092714	1200/60	32	37.5	1st layer - 22 ³ 0
P2	FL195	093100	093620	100/s	29	37.8	
R3	FL140	093635	095142	1200/60			2.5 x 10 ³
P3	FL	095206	095758	100/s	27		Some branching in layer
R4	1000'	100547	102120	1200/60	26	37.8	0.1 x 10 ¹¹
P4	1000'	102145	102834	100/s	27	37.5	
R5	4000'	113134	114621	200/s	27	37.5	4.1E ³ - 1.0E ³
P5	4000'	114643	115013	200/s			are good plus numbers 11.50 26 1200/60
P6		121506	122030	200/s	31	37.8	Some single points
R6	6000'	122156	123858	100/s			instrument structure
P7	6000'	124151	125323	200/s			
P8	FL1	125339	125959	100/s	33	37.5	
R8-1		130008	130213	100/s			ALS450 comp lost
R	FL240	130340	134905	1200/60	23	37.5	

b438 nevzorov plot 1.bmp

b438 nevzorov plot 2.bmp

LEOSPHERE
Lidar Environmental Observations
1.9.44

Mode: Client

User: Joss Kent

Comments: B438

AA: 0 ZA: 0

SETTING

START STOP QUIT

FL240 South → North

1.9.44

Mode Client

User Joss Kent

Comments B438

AA 0 ZA 0

SETTING

START STOP QUIT

Duration 00:14:16

Profile 79

Shots 161/200

Laser PM Acq Scan GPS PTU
space disk used % 7

Calibrated Raw Signal Corrected Signal Extinction and Backscatter PBL-Clouds-O.Depth Corrected Signal - Temporal BSR-Temporal

Run at 400ft Hdy north. G(A)

1.9.44

Mode Client

User Joss Kent

Comments B438

AA 0 ZA 0

SETTING

START STOP QUIT

Duration 00:39:12

Profile 38

Shots 203/1200

Laser PM Acq Scan GPS PTU
space disk used % 8

Calibrated Raw Signal Corrected Signal Extinction and Backscatter PBL-Clouds-O.Depth Corrected Signal - Temporal BSR-Temporal

F2240 South -> North

1.9.44

Mode Client

User Joss Kent

Comments B438

AA 0 ZA 0

SETTING

START STOP QUIT

Duration 00:01:58

Profile 19

Shots 86/100

Laser PM Acq Scan GPS PTU
space disk used % 7

Calibrated Raw Signal Corrected Signal Extinction and Backscatter PBL-Clouds-O.Depth Corrected Signal - Temporal BSR-Temporal

Flight B438 11:51:45

Heading 6 deg Speed 230 knots Height 0.1kft Press 1006mb

Lat 23°0.0'N Long 60°30.0'E Wind 3 ms-1/ 173 deg

Temp 29.48C Dewpoint 26.93C

From 10:00:00 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	1006.55	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	29.49	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	26.94	deg C

*Run 1 FC210
5 and P5 (100 ft)*

Flight B438 11:54:50

Heading 198 deg Speed 233 knots Height 0.7kft Press 987mb

Lat 23°0.0'N Long 60°30.0'E Wind 8 ms-1/ 212 deg

Temp 32.92C Dewpoint -6.25C

From 10:31:33 to now

Current values		
+++++ STATIC PRESSURE	987.07	mb
+++++ DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	32.92	deg C
+++++ DEW POINT	-6.25	deg C

P2, P3, P4 + P5.

New plot, same times

Flight B438 12:38:30

Heading 4 deg Speed 228 knots Height 6.0kft Press 810mb

Lat 22°42.0'N Long 60°30.0'E Wind 6 ms-1/ 86 deg

Temp 20.44C Dewpoint -10.62C

From 09:33:24 to now

Current values			
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	45510	secs	⊙ All
NEPH BLUE SP	55.64	m-1	○
NEPH GREEN SP	51.02	m-1	○
NEPH RED SP	51.45	m-1	○

Run 7 600ft north hand

Flight B438 13:02:09

Heading 180 deg Speed 318 knots Height 23.9kft Press 392mb

Lat 21°6.0'N Long 60°30.0'E Wind 3 ms-1/ 17 deg

Temp -19.03C Dewpoint -43.31C

From 12:15:00 to now

	Current values		
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	24	Kft
-----	NEPH BLUE SP	5.22	m-1
-----	NEPH GREEN SP	6.23	m-1
-----	NEPH RED SP	4.7	m-1

P6

Flight B438 13:02:19

Heading 180 deg Speed 316 knots Height 23.9kft Press 392mb

Lat 21°6.0'N Long 60°30.0'E Wind 3 ms-1/ 17 deg

Temp -19.04C Dewpoint -43.4C

From 12:15:00 to now

Current values			
STATIC PRESSURE		392.74	mb
DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	++++	-19.05	deg C
DEW POINT	-----	-43.4	deg C

P6

Flight B438 12:22:18

Heading 35 deg Speed 231 knots Height 6.0kft Press 810mb

Lat 21°42.0'N Long 60°24.0'E Wind 8 ms-1/ 108 deg

Temp 19.05C Dewpoint -8.57C

From 10:33:00 to now

Current values
PRESSURE HEIGHT 6.06 Kft
REFRACTMITY 229.16 Munits
⊙ All
○

P2 to PG

New plot, same times**Flight B438 12:35:14**

Heading 5 deg Speed 232 knots Height 6.0kft Press 811mb

Lat 22°30.0'N Long 60°30.0'E Wind 8 ms-1/ 89 deg

Temp 20.26C Dewpoint -12.06C

From 11:33:14 to now

Current values				
---	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	45312	secs	<input type="checkbox"/> All
---	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	293.43	K	<input type="checkbox"/>
---	DEW POINT	-12.07	deg C	<input type="checkbox"/>
---	REFRACTIVITY	225.07	Munits	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Supra dust

LEOSPHERE
Lidar Environmental Observations
1.9.44

Mode: Client

User: Joss Kent

Comments: B438

AA: 0 ZA: 0

SETTING

START STOP QUIT

Duration: 00:17:00

Profile: 190

Shots: 75/100

Laser PM Acq Scan GPS PTU

space disk used %: 7

Run at 6000 ft.

LEOSPHERE
Lidar Environmental Observations

1.9.14

Mode: Client

User: Joss Kent

Comments: B438

Calibrated Raw Signal | Corrected Signal | Extinction and Backscatter | PBL-Clouds-O.Depth | Corrected Signal - Temporal | BSR-Temporal

0 45 90

AA 0 ZA 0

SETTING

START STOP QUIT

Duration 00:17:00

Profile 190

Shots 75/100

Laser PM Acq Scan GPS PTU

space disk used % 7

Run 2 6000ft

~~JHM~~
Zakoff Profile

Flight B438 09:49:11

Heading 94 deg Speed 307 knots Height 21.0kft Press 445mb

Lat 23°30.0'N Long 59°48.0'E Wind 3 ms-1/ 298 deg

Temp -11.57C Dewpoint -28.39C

From 09:33:24 to now

Current values				
-----	PRESSURE HEIGHT	21.03	Kft	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
-----	NEPH BLUE SP	0.05	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
-----	NEPH GREEN SP	0.67	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
-----	NEPH RED SP	-0.88	m-1	<input type="radio"/>

TAKE OFF PROFILE

Flight B438 11:48:01

Heading 1 deg Speed 226 knots Height 2.6kft Press 918mb

Lat 22°42.0'N Long 60°30.0'E Wind 1 ms-1/ 183 deg

Temp 28.99C Dewpoint -6.83C

From 11:31:33 to 11:46:36

Current values				
-----	GPS LATITUDE	22.8	deg (+ve N)	● All
-----	NEPH BLUE SP	94.61	m-1	○
-----	NEPH GREEN SP	100.77	m-1	○
-----	NEPH RED SP	107.21	m-1	○

Flight B438 11:23:53

Heading 178 deg Speed 230 knots Height 7.2kft Press 773mb

Lat 21°54.0'N Long 60°30.0'E Wind 8 ms-1/ 113 deg

Temp 16.24C Dewpoint -6.0C

From 11:05:59 to 11:21:05

Current values			
+++++ POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE	311.44	K	● All
NEPH BLUE SP	60.84	m-1	○

LEOSPHERE
Lidar Environmental Observations
1.9.44

Mode: Client

User: Joss Kent

Comments: B438

AA: 0 ZA: 0

SETTING

START STOP QUIT

Duration: 00:00:00

Profile: 63

Shots: 90/100

Laser PM Acq Scan GPS PTU

space disk used %: 7

Calibrated Raw Signal | Corrected Signal | Extinction and Backscatter | PBL-Clouds-O.Depth | Corrected Signal - Temporal | BSR-Temporal

Descending ~~cont~~ Run at ~~10:00:00~~ / 4.
14000h

Flight B438 09:55:11

Heading 94 deg Speed 320 knots Height 21.0kft Press 445mb

Lat 23°30.0'N Long 60°18.0'E Wind 1 ms-1/ 337 deg

Temp -12.14C Dewpoint -26.4C

From start to now

Current values			
++++	STATIC PRESSURE	445.76	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-12.14	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-26.41	deg C

climb out Muscat

Clear
Take off profile

Flight B438 09:48:58

Heading 94 deg Speed 306 knots Height 21.0kft Press 445mb

Lat 23°30.0'N Long 59°42.0'E Wind 3 ms-1/ 297 deg

Temp -11.61C Dewpoint -28.02C

From 09:33:24 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	445.67	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-11.62	deg C
-----	DEW POINT	-28.02	deg C

Flight B438 09:49:27

Heading 94 deg Speed 308 knots Height 21.0kft Press 445mb

Lat 23°30.0'N Long 59°48.0'E Wind 3 ms-1/ 300 deg

Temp -11.65C Dewpoint -29.03C

From 09:33:24 to now

Current values			
-----	PRESSURE HEIGHT	21.04	Kft
	INS WIND ANGLE	300.18	deg
			<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
			<input type="radio"/>

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 09Z on 26/04/2009, from 00Z on 26/04/2009

Surface Dust concentration T+009

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 09Z on 26/04/2009, from 00Z on 26/04/2009

850hPa Dust concentration T+009

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 09Z on 26/04/2009, from 00Z on 26/04/2009

700hPa Dust concentration T+009

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 09Z on 26/04/2009, from 12Z on 25/04/2009

Dust concentration (log1) T+021

Southern Asia CAM Aerosol Optical Depth
At 09Z on 26/04/2009, from 12Z on 25/04/2009

AOD T+021

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 09Z on 26/04/2009, from 12Z on 25/04/2009

850hPa Dust concentration T+021

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 09Z on 26/04/2009, from 12Z on 25/04/2009

Surface Dust concentration T+021

Flight B438 11:51:38

Heading 6 deg Speed 237 knots Height 0.1kft Press 1008mb

Lat 23°0.0'N Long 60°30.0'E Wind 3 ms-1/ 166 deg

Temp 29.44C Dewpoint 21.86C

From 10:00:00 to now

Current values			
-----	0.14	Kft	● All
-----	73.57	m-1	○
-----	71.39	m-1	○
-----	69.97	m-1	○

Run (FL200) to end P5 (100kt)

FNMOC 18km COAMPS 2009042512 run $\tau = 18$ h

VT: Sun 06Z 26 APR 09

Dust Optical Depth 018 HR FCST

COAMPS Data Courtesy of Fleet Numerical Meteorology and Oceanography Center, Monterey, CA
GrADS (<http://grads.iges.org/grads>) Graphics by D.J.Laws FNMOC Code N36 AI (dennis.laws@navy.mil)

Southern Asia CAM Aerosol Optical Depth
At 09Z on 26/04/2009, from 00Z on 26/04/2009

AOD T+009

0.05 0.1 0.2 0.4 0.8 1.6 3.2 6.4 12.8

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 09Z on 26/04/2009, from 00Z on 26/04/2009

Dust concentration (log1) T+009

